

AURORA

AURORA

Research & Innovation

Open Science Monitor

Deliverable 6.1 -
Accompanying report

Horizon 2020
European Union funding
for Research & Innovation

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Executive Summary

This report serves as an accompanying document to AURORA RI deliverable 6.1 - *Adding an Open science function to the SDG dashboard*.

We describe how we created the [Aurora Open Science monitor](#) by making use of proven components (e.g. OpenAIRE Graph, OpenAIRE Connect and OpenAIRE Monitor) from the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Services catalogue. The Aurora Open Science Monitor allows Aurora to align with future EU mandates (via policy and grants) for research evaluation, monitoring, and assessment.

In this report, we describe:

- ▲ Our partnership with OpenAIRE
- ▲ A step-by-step guide to set up the connection between institutional repositories of meta-information and the OpenAIRE Connect Gateway
- ▲ The features of the OpenAIRE Monitor
- ▲ Future developments for this partnership

We aim to provide a blueprint for other Research Initiatives to follow the same path.

Project Abstract

Aurora was formed in 2016 as a consortium of research-intensive universities deeply committed to the social impact of their activities. The objective of Aurora is to match academic excellence with societal relevance. One of the core values of Aurora is to learn from and with each other and the AURORA RI project is an important part in realising this.

The AURORA RI project develops closer research and innovation support structures to complement the excellent research and innovation activities within the Aurora Alliance, a European Universities Initiative funded by the European Commission. It will further deepen and expand the cooperation among these universities and strengthen their identity as research-intensive universities dedicated to societal impact. The aim of AURORA RI is to develop a research and innovation support agenda framed by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and based on the four priority domains of the Alliance:

1. Sustainability and Climate Change
2. Digital Society and Global Citizenship
3. Health and Wellbeing; and
4. Culture: Diversity and Identity.

The project focus is to identify and achieve an understanding of best practices and policies on sharing research infrastructure and resources, cooperation on open science and entrepreneurial activity, empowering human capital, and mainstreaming citizen engagement. Throughout the project we analyse and map best practices already in place, learning from each other. We define barriers to cooperation at national and international level and find ways to overcome them where possible. The findings will create the basis for our Research & Innovation support agenda and will be shared with the other European Universities and beyond. The actions implemented during the project period aim at creating a platform for cooperation that will sustain beyond the lifetime of the project and equip researchers and students at Aurora Alliance Universities with a broad toolkit to conduct excellent research and disruptive innovation.

AURORA RI Work Package 6: Open Science

Academia is in a transition towards a more transparent way of doing and sharing scientific research. This shift to Open Science increases the accessibility of research, which contributes to research integrity and opens new avenues for collaboration with other researchers and societal partners. In Work Package 6 of AURORA RI, we focus on *Sharing and implementing Open Science practices*. Within this Work Package, we have defined three tasks and four deliverables:

1. Building a shared knowledge base of Open Science resources, policies, and practices

In this task, meta-information about research outputs, resources, policies, experiences, and practices on Open Science are collected from Aurora partners and beyond. The meta-information for Aurora partners is aggregated into an Open Science Monitor, and the best practices are collected in a knowledge base. This knowledge base allows the Aurora partners to learn from each other's choices and experiences. It is made freely available, so others beyond the Aurora Alliance may also benefit from it.

▲ *Deliverable 6.1 - Open science function to the SDG dashboard*

▲ *Deliverable 6.2 - A shared knowledge base of Open Science resources, policies, and best practices*

2. Establish a joint training programme on Open Science

Building on the existing Aurora Open Education database and the knowledge base from Task 1, we establish Open Science training modules. These are aimed at helping students and researchers to incorporate Open Science practices into their research workflows and to become ambassadors for Open Science. Topics that will be covered are Open Access publishing; how to make research data and software FAIR; how to guarantee research integrity; and how to engage with the general public about research. The educational resources for these training sessions will be made freely available.

▲ *Deliverable 6.3 - Open Science training modules*

3. Creation of a network of Open Science researcher communities within and between the Aurora institutions.

A network of Open Science communities is created within and between the Aurora institutions. In these Open Science communities, students and researchers who want to learn about Open Science can share experiences and inspire each other. A platform will be created in which local communities within the Aurora Alliance institutions can interact with communities from other institutions, allowing for international collaboration.

▲ *Deliverable 6.4 - Open Science Community starter kit and a platform for these communities to interact*

Introduction

This deliverable is the result of work carried out within the Aurora partner universities as part of the Erasmus+ funded Aurora Alliance and the Horizon 2020 funded AURORA RI projects.

In the Aurora Alliance project, a [dashboard](#) was developed to exhibit the connection between Aurora research output and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The original idea for the AURORA RI deliverable 6.1 was to add a tab on Open Science to that dashboard.

However, in 2022, Aurora entered into a partnership with OpenAIRE, which allowed us to go beyond the original plan by embedding our research meta-information on Open Science-practices and relation to the SDGs within the established OpenAIRE infrastructures and services to create an [Aurora Open Science monitor](#).

In this report, we will describe:

- ▲ Our partnership with OpenAIRE
- ▲ A step-by-step guide to set up the connection between institutional repositories of meta-information and the OpenAIRE Connect Gateway
- ▲ The features of the OpenAIRE Monitor
- ▲ Future developments for this partnership

Partnership with OpenAIRE

On May 17th, 2022, Aurora and the OpenAIRE-Nexus consortium¹ signed a [memorandum of understanding](#) to start a formal collaboration on registering research outputs to monitor Open Science practices, map research output to the SDGs and provide new functionalities like SDG-oriented discovery and statistics to the OpenAIRE Monitor. [OpenAIRE](#) is a non-profit organisation that contains a service catalogue for sustaining Open Science information services as part of the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#).

As part of the collaboration, Aurora provides its [Aurora SDG text classification service](#) that enables everyone to map academic texts in multiple European languages to the SDGs. This includes a service in which a researcher can insert the abstract of their research paper, which returns the predicted values of how much this abstract is related to the 17 SDGs, based on a multilingual AI. Additionally, it generates an SDG doughnut with the relative SDG predictions, which can be used as a badge along with a research paper.

OpenAIRE in turn ingests the meta-information from Aurora Universities' research outputs in the [OpenAIRE Graph](#). This content is enriched and accessible through a [Connect Gateway](#), a single entry-point to all academic publications, data sets, research projects, software and other research outputs of the Aurora universities. In addition, the [Monitor Dashboard](#) offers insight into the uptake of Open Science practices and the connection with the SDGs. These three OpenAIRE services, and how they were combined to create this deliverable, will be described in more detail below.

¹ The Horizon 2020 [OpenAIRE-Nexus project](#), a consortium of 11 partners, brings in Europe, EOSC and the world a set of services to implement and accelerate Open Science and tools to embed in researchers' workflows, making it easier for them to accept and uptake Open Science practices of openness and FAIRness.

Furthermore, OpenAIRE and Aurora will collaborate on training: Aurora will include OpenAIRE services like [Amnesia](#) for data anonymisation, [Argos](#) for data management, [Zenodo](#) for data deposition, and [EpiScience](#) for setting up Open Access journals in its training courses on Open Science practices; OpenAIRE will exploit the program and outputs of the Aurora Open Science project to improve the documentation and training on the [services of the Nexus portfolio](#).

Adding linked information to a global Open Science Graph

In the transition to Open Science, researchers are opening up their research process by sharing not only final research outputs (e.g., the publication), but also other products like datasets, software, hypotheses (e.g. preregistrations), protocols/methods, experiments, and their meta-information. These outputs are often published in different archives and repositories and rely on persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI, ORCID, Grid.ac, PDBs) to be linked to each other and the author, to other research products (e.g. through [supplementedBy](#), [citedBy](#), [versionOf](#)), and possibly to related projects and/or relative funders. This creates a massive collection of objects interlinked by semantic relationships: the Research Graph.

The [OpenAIRE Graph](#) includes meta-information and links between scientific products (e.g. literature, datasets, software, and "other research products"), organisations, funders, funding streams, projects, communities, and (provenance) data sources.

The principles of the Research Graph are as follows:

- ▲ **Open and transparent.** It is available for download and re-use as CC-BY (due to some input sources whose licence is CC-BY); parts of the graphs can be re-used as CC-0; provenance is tracked at the level of the records and, when these are the result of full-text mining, of the properties (provenance also includes an indicator of trust, in the range [0..1]).
- ▲ **Decentralized and interoperable.** Metadata and links are collected from data sources, such as institutional/data/software repositories, publishers, registries, and re-distributed to such sources via brokering services.
- ▲ **Intelligent linking.** Abstracts, full-texts of Open Access publications and links are processed by several algorithms that infer new links and enrich the graph.
- ▲ **Embedded metrics.** Powers up calculation of advanced statistics and metrics about Open Science and research impact.

Aggregating research information into the OpenAIRE Connect Gateway

The OpenAIRE [Connect](#) Gateway enables institutions, universities, or lead teams on a scientific domain to easily create, configure and manage their own customised web portals (aka Gateways) for the discovery of research outcomes that are of interest to their audiences. Thanks to its high configurability, a Connect Gateway can be customised with the community identity and be a single-entry point to the research products relevant for the community among everything that is available in the OpenAIRE Research Graph.

With the collaboration between Aurora and OpenAIRE, features to view the contribution of research outputs to the SDGs is now possible.

A step-by-step guide to setup a Research Portal using OpenAIRE Connect:

To aggregate the research meta-information into a gateway, steps need to be taken. Some of these require action from a coordinator; others require actions from repository or Current Research Information System (CRIS) managers at the individual institutions.

Once the gateway is set-up, the research meta-information is automatically added to the Open Science monitor (see below).

Step	Actions for coordinator	Actions for institution
1	<p><u>Request an OpenAIRE Connect portal.</u></p> <p>Arrange a training session with OpenAIRE for Repository / CRIS Managers, to prepare them for step 6, 7 and 8.</p>	
2	<p>Make a list of Participating Institutions, including their CRISs, Literature and Data Repositories and Bibliographic catalogues, the URLS's and the contact persons administering these systems.</p>	<p>Provide a list of your Institutional CRISs, Literature and Data Repositories and Bibliographic catalogues, the URLS's and the contact persons administering these systems.</p>
3	<p>Monitor if these systems are publicly accessible on the web.</p>	<p>Make your repository/CRIS publicly accessible.</p>
4	<p>Monitor crawlability of to-be-added systems.</p> <p>Test if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▲ the sitemap.xml is available and mentioned in the robot.txt. ▲ metatags or micro-labels are present on the html-details pages. 	<p>Make sure your system is crawlable by search engine spiders, especially from Google Scholar. Follow these guidelines: https://scholar.google.com/intl/nl/scholar/inclusion.html</p> <p>You can add a sitemap.xml in your robots.txt, and add metatags or schema.org micro-labels on your html details pages.</p>

Step	Actions for coordinator	Actions for institution
5	<p>Monitor registration in directories. Check if the repository/ CRIS is available in the directories OpenDOAR, DRIS and RE3Data</p>	<p>Register/update your repository/ CRIS in OpenDOAR (directory of Literature Repositories, DRIS (directory euroCRIS), or RE3Data (directory of data repositories)</p>
6	<p>Monitor harvestability. Check:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▲ the OAI-PMH API on accessibility ▲ the expected number of records (all, not only containing a full-text document) 	<p>Make sure your records can be harvested by OpenAIRE (and other services). Provide an OAI-PMH API (protocol for metadata harvesting) to the coordinator. Expose all metadata records (not only full-text Open Access) in a public OAI-PMH interface. Make sure the OpenAIRE harvester can pass through your firewall.</p>
7	<p>Monitor system registration in OpenAIRE. Check in https://provide.openaire.eu if the repository/ CRIS is flagged as “registered”.</p>	<p>Register your repository/ CRIS in https://provide.openaire.eu by creating an OpenAIRE account, login, finding your repository/ CRIS in the list, and registering it.</p>
8	<p>Monitor OpenAIRE compliancy. Get validation reports from repository/ CRIS admin.</p>	<p>Make sure your repository/ CRIS is compliant with OpenAIRE metadata standards by using the Validator. Send validation reports to the Coordinator.</p>
9	<p>Manage the OpenAIRE Connect portal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▲ Add a portal title, description logo, and colour scheme. ▲ Add repository/ CRIS administrators as managers to the OpenAIRE Connect Gateway ▲ Monitor if managers are visible in the list of curators (e.g. https://aurora.openaire.eu/curators) 	<p>Update your curator profile on the OpenAIRE Connect Gateway through an invite link from the Coordinator.</p>

Step	Actions for coordinator	Actions for institution
10	<p>Monitor organisations and their repositories/ CRISs in the OpenAIRE Connect Gateway:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▲ Check if the participating organisation is visible in the organisations list (e.g. https://aurora.openaire.eu/organisations) ▲ Check if the repository/ CRIS appears in the Content providers list (e.g. https://aurora.openaire.eu/search/find/dataproviders) 	<p>Add Organisation and repository/ CRIS research output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▲ Add your organisation in the organisation tab. ▲ Add your repository/ CRIS in the data sources tab
11	<p>Facilitate Affiliation identification cleaning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▲ Provide an online table with the ROR identifier for each organisation. ▲ Provide an online table where repository/ CRIS administrators can add OpenAIRE-organisation-identifiers and mark them to be “is_same_as” the main organisation, or “is_child_of” the main organisation. ▲ Check if your contact person from a National Open Access Desk (NOAD) made the changes by comparing the version of the main organisation with the table provided by the repository/ CRIS administrators. 	<p>This exercise will make sure the correct publications and data sets will be attributed to the correct affiliation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▲ Search for the name variants and abbreviations of your organisation in the OpenAIRE Explore Advanced search for Organisations. ▲ Write down the name and URL and OrganisationID in the provided table from the Coordinator. ▲ Mark them to be “is_same_as” the main organisation, or “is_child_of” the main organisation. ▲ Send a request to your NOAD to make the changes in the organisational structure of the OpenAIRE Open Organisations service.
12	<p>Add Funder Projects and related publications.</p> <p>Ask OpenAIRE to add Funder projects based on the main organisation, as adjusted in step 11.</p> <p>This will result in extra publications and data sets that have mentioned Funder grants.</p>	
13	<p>Request to set up the OpenAIRE Monitor for your Gateway content.</p>	

Monitoring Open Science with the OpenAIRE Monitor

Once the Aurora Gateway is operational, the aggregated meta-information can be used in an OpenAIRE Monitor dashboard. This can be set up by the coordinator by [requesting access to the OpenAIRE Monitor](#). The dashboard can be [customised](#) such that other managers and members can get editing rights. The look can be configured to match your brand, and the sections tabs and charts can be made publicly visible, restricted to members, or hidden.

This is the resulting [Aurora Open Science Monitor](#).

Indicators

The [possible indicators in the Monitor](#) fall into five groups:

1. Research outputs (including number of publications, data sets, software, and other output)
2. Open Science attributes of the research outputs (e.g., FAIRness, Open Access, Journal business models, APC's, Plan-S compliancy)
3. Collaborations (by project participation, by co-authorship)
4. Impact (downloads, citations, SDG relatedness). Part of the collaboration between Aurora and OpenAIRE focuses on enriching the SDG-indicator in the OpenAIRE Monitor. Aurora has provided feedback on SDG indicators and their [use cases](#), using the [Aurora SDG Research Dashboard](#). A report on “Aurora indicators for SDG's in OpenAIRE Monitor” is available [here](#).
5. Funding (relationship to funded grants/ projects)

Future developments

Adding new partners and their repositories/ CRISs

Aurora Universities from Iceland, Innsbruck, and Olomouc are working on making their CRIS systems operational. This will result in more validated research output. Furthermore, Paris-East Créteil University (UPEC) recently joined and is working on building a separate set of publications in HAL representing their research output.

Using the monitor for validated and transparent reporting on Open Science and Research Assessment

The EU is monitoring [Open Access](#) and [Open Science](#) using the data from the OpenAIRE Research Graph. Connecting to the OpenAIRE Research Graph enables European institutions to report correctly on their Open Access, Open Science, and new advances in Research Assessment (e.g., the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#)).

SDGs on the Impact Monitor

We are in contact with OpenAIRE to share Aurora's lessons-learned on the user needs for the SDG-indicator in the OpenAIRE Monitor. These blueprints will be used to [develop the SDG Impact page](#) (coming soon) on the Monitor. This will ultimately benefit other research organisations as well, reaching beyond the scope of Aurora.

Appendix I - Aurora Gateway Frontend

AURORA Home Deposit Link Search About Develop Manage mV

Aurora Open Science Monitor 🗨 Aurora SDG Research Dashboard 🗨

Aurora Universities Network

Type: Research products | Scholarly works: Search in OpenAIRE 🔍

[Summary](#) | Publications (834,041) | Research data (37,069) | Research software (196) | Other research products (27,433)

[Member](#) [Invite users](#)

Aurora consists of research-intensive universities deeply committed to the social impact of our activities, and with a history of engagement with the communities in which we operate. Our overall vision is to use our academic excellence to influence societal change through our research and education - aiming to contribute to the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.

All our research output is combined via this [Aurora Connect Gateway](#), and put on the [Aurora Monitor Dashboard](#).

More about Aurora: <https://aurora-universities.eu/>

Curated by: Maurice Vanderfeesten, Baldwin Zariroh, Sander Bosch

Created: 30-Nov-2021

Projects: 1,516 ⓘ

Linked Zenodo Communities: 2 ⓘ

Members: 12

Content Providers: 37 ⓘ

Supporting Organizations

[BROWSE ALL](#) →

ps://aurora.openaire.eu

Appendix II - Aurora Gateway Backend

AURORA Home Deposit Link Search About Develop Manage mv

Admin Dashboard Manage Users
Aurora Universities Network

Managers Members Notification settings Links Personal info

Managers Pending managers INVITE MANAGER

7 Managers, Page 1 of 1

maurice.vanderfeesten@vu.nl	bmz@hi.is
thomas.haselwanter@ulbk.ac.at	felix.schmidt@uni-due.de
ignasi.salvado@urv.cat	elena.dellaquila@unina.it
s.e.bosch@vu.nl	

Add Managers

AURORA Home Deposit Link Search About Develop Manage mv

Admin Dashboard Manage Personal info & Affiliations
Aurora Universities Network

Managers Members Notification settings Links Personal info

RESET SAVE

Name *
Maurice Vanderfeesten
 Visible

Biography

My Affiliations

+ ADD NEW AFFILIATION

Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
URL: <https://vu.nl>

EDIT DELETE

Your personal info will be visible in the Curators page of your Community Gateway. Read [privacy policy statement](#).

Add Manager details and bio

Add Data Sources or Content Providers (Literature and Data repositories, and CRIS systems)

Admin Dashboard / Manage Data Sources
Aurora Universities Network

Profile Organizations Projects **Data sources** Subjects Zenodo Communities

37 Data Sources, Page 1 of 4

Archivio della ricerca - Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II	Repositori Institucional URV
University of East Anglia digital repository	DuEPublico - Duisburg-Essen Publications Online
Opin visindi	University of Innsbruck Digital Library
Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II Open Archive	RESEARCH TRENDS IN HUMANITIES Education & Philosophy
TeMA: Journal of Land Use, Mobility and Environment	Reti Medievali Rivista

Home Deposit Link Search About Develop Manage

Admin Dashboard Manage Projects

Aurora Universities Network

Profile
Organizations
Projects
Data sources
Subjects
Zenodo Communities

+ NEW PROJECT

1,516 Projects, Page 1 of 152

FILTER BY FUNDER ▾

Sort by
Title ▾

1 2 3 4 5 >

<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">"The "Hidden Architecture" of Organizations: A Study of Organizational Secrecy" [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: 331644 Funder: EC FP7</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>	<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">"Fragments, Blotches Healing Lights: The Conversation Between Film and Poetry in the Post-War American Avant-Garde" [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: AH/D501288/1 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>
<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">"Look with thine ears": A Century of Shakespearean BBC Radio Adaptation. [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: 2277382 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>	<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">"What football players do .. is part of the kids lives": Exploring the connections between young people and sporting celebrity [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: AH/M00919X/1 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>
<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">(In)Consistency of responses to self-assessed health measures and implications for biosocial research [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: ES/V003356/1 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>	<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">13 ERA IB: Production of new bioactive compounds by plants and bacteria using new and improved halogenases [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: BB/M004570/1 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>
<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">2-representation theory and categorification [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: EP/S017216/1 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>	<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">21st century truffle production: the application of chemical biology (GANESAN_U17ICASE) [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: 1941430 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>
<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">3D probing of the atmospheric boundary layer and volcanic plumes: Proof of concept [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: NE/H01009X/1 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>	<p style="font-size: 10px; font-weight: bold;">50 Years on From the Sæmaul Undong Movement: A Long-term Economic & Environmental Analysis [📄]</p> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Grant ID: 2408894 Funder: UKRI</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: 8px; font-weight: bold;">— REMOVE</p>

1 2 3 4 5 >

Add Funder Projects

Appendix III - Aurora Monitor Frontend

Appendix IV - Aurora Monitor Backend

The screenshot shows the 'Manage Profile' interface for 'Aurora Universities Network'. The page includes a sidebar with navigation options: General, Indicators, Users, and a search bar for 'Manage profiles'. The main content area contains several form fields:

- Name ***: Aurora Universities Network
- URL Alias ***: aurora
- Index ID ***: aurora
- Index Name ***: Aurora Universities Net...
- Index Short Name ***: Aurora Universities Net...
- Description**: Aurora consists of research-intensive universities deeply committed to the social impact of our activities, and with a history of engagement with the communities in which we operate. Our overall vision is to use our academic excellence to influence societal change through our research and education - aiming to contribute to the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.
- Upload options**: An 'UPLOAD A FILE' button or a 'Link to the logo' field containing the URL: <https://explore.openaire.eu/utlis-service/download/aurora-1644397211214.png>
- Select a status ***: Public
- Select a type ***: Research Initiative
- Notify Managers

A green 'Add Information' button is visible in the top right corner of the interface.

